

UDC 535.375.51:539.194+621.396.67.091.22

Self-Consistent Model for Enhancement of the Raman Scattering of Polarized Light in Azo-Polymer Film with a Plasmonic Nanoantenna

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Abstract

This article¹ is devoted to the simulation of Raman scattering in the “antenna-sample” system. The system consists of an anisotropic azo-dye molecule covalently attached to a polymer chain and a plasmonic antenna located near the molecule. A model of near-field interaction in a system of dipoles is proposed. The model takes into account the change in the polarizabilities both of the antenna and of the molecule due to the mutual influence of their near field on each other. Based on the proposed model, spectra of tip-enhanced Raman scattering in longitudinally and transversely polarized field for both isomers of azo-chromophore were simulated. The static polarizability of the molecule and the Raman-tensors of the vibration modes are determined performing the quantum chemical calculations of a molecule with one monomer according to the density functional theory. It is shown that NO₂ moiety orientation in respect to the molecular dipole moment can be determined from the TERS spectra improving conformational analysis at the nanoscale.

Key words: azo-chromophore, azo-polymer film, plasmonic antenna, tip-enhanced Raman scattering, near-field polarization, density functional theory, polarizability tensor, Raman tensor

1. Introduction

Polymers that contain azo-chromophore molecules covalently bonded to a polymer chain are functional materials that allow the orientation of azo-chromophores to be used to store information [1]. Due to diffraction, the minimum storage volume is determined by the focal spot size. With the help of near-field optics, it is theoretically possible to reduce the minimum storage volume down to the size of a few chromophores, which can potentially increase the recording density from ~ 160 MB/cm² to 10^7 MB/cm² due to the localization of light. To characterize the orientation of an azo-chromophore in three dimensions at the nanoscale, polarization-controlled tip-enhanced Raman spectroscopy (TERS) can be used in combination with atomic force microscopy (AFM) [1,2]. Raman scattering is enhanced only near the probe, or optical antenna, that converts free-space electromagnetic waves into a localized near field [3,4]. The use of the near field allows one to control the polarization of light in all three dimensions; therefore, it becomes possible

¹This is the translation of the article originally published in Russian. The original version can be found at <http://mi.mathnet.ru/eng/uzku1431>. Cite article as: Gazizov A.R., Kharintsev S.S., Salakhov M.Kh. Self-consistent model for enhancement of the Raman scattering of polarized light in azo-polymer film with a plasmonic nanoantenna. *Uchenye Zapiski Kazanskogo Universiteta. Seriya Fiziko-Matematicheskie Nauki*, **2018**, vol. 160, no. 1, pp. 61–71. (In Russian) doi:10.5281/zenodo.3240055

to experimentally reconstruct the components of the Raman tensor. In the last decade, TERS with near-field polarization control has been used to determine the direction of the dipole moment of a nanoantenna [5, 6], to determine the intrinsic symmetry of the sample and to study local mechanical stresses [7, 8]. Recently, various models were proposed by the groups of R. Ossikovsky [9], L. Novotny [10, 11], P. Verma [5] for evaluation of the near-field polarization. In all these models, the enhancement factor of the nanoantenna for this problem is considered to be known *a priori*. As a result of the enhancement, the TERS spectrum of the molecule can significantly differ compared to the conventional Raman spectrum. There is a demand for a theoretical description of the enhancement of Raman scattering in “tip-sample” system, when the enhancement factor is not known in advance, in order to predict the TERS spectra in case of the anisotropic molecule.

The aim of this work is to study the effects of enhancement and other changes in the Raman spectra in longitudinal and transverse polarizations. We investigate how exactly the Raman spectrum of a molecule changes in the presence of an anisotropic probe. The considered azo-chromophore was a 4-amino-4'-nitroazobenzene molecule (disperse orange 3, DO3) in the form of cis- and trans- isomers, covalently bonded to the CFAO polymer unit [12]. The Raman polarizabilities were calculated numerically using the density functional theory method (DFT). A prolate spheroidal gold nanoparticle with a radius of curvature of 25 nm at the tip and an eccentricity of 0.7 was used as a model of the tapered optical antenna.

2. Results and discussion

When considering light scattering problem in the “tip-sample” system in near-field optical microscopy, L. Novotny in his articles (for example, in [3]) treat it as superposition of elementary processes of interaction between the probe and the sample, which both scatter the incident radiation \mathbf{E}_{in} . Each of these interactions, in turn, is represented in the form of successive independent processes of light propagation and scattering on an object. Thus, the total radiated field \mathbf{E}_{out} can be written as a sum; the subscripts for each term indicate the order in which objects (sample S or probe P) scatter or emit radiation:

$$\mathbf{E}_{out} = \mathbf{E}_S + \mathbf{E}_P + \mathbf{E}_{SP} + \mathbf{E}_{PS} + \mathbf{E}_{SPS} + \mathbf{E}_{PSP} + \dots$$

In that model, TERS spectroscopy corresponds to the \mathbf{E}_{PSP} term, but with input and output frequencies differ by an amount corresponding to the energy of vibrational modes. However, in that kind of treatment it is impossible to account the fact that different samples require their own enhancement factor, which becomes dependent on the sample. Generally speaking, the combined “tip-sample” system can be described using one Green’s function $\mathbf{G} = \mathbf{G}_P + \mathbf{G}_S$, where \mathbf{G}_P and \mathbf{G}_S are the Green’s functions of the probe and the sample, respectively. The problem, however, is that \mathbf{G}_S is defined in the presence of the probe and does not reflect the properties of the sample separately from the probe [3].

In the work of R. Ossikovski’s group [13], it was shown that depolarization of the incident light at the tip of the nanoantenna lead to selective enhancement of the response of certain vibration modes. From the available experimental works [3–8, 13], one can conclude that selective enhancement is rooted in the anisotropy of the nanoantenna’s polarizability tensor, as well as its dependence on the sample properties.

In our approach, dipole moments additionally excited by the probe and the molecule on each other through mutual induction are taken into account, since the local field at their locations differs from the incident field. Typically, the electric field around the

Figure 1. The structure of the Disperse Orange 3 (DO3) molecule attached to the CFAO polymer.

tip of the nanoantenna is determined using the formalism of the Green's function [14]. In the point-dipole approximation, the electric field in the “tip-sample” system can be written as follows:

$$\mathbf{E}_2(\mathbf{r}, \omega) = \mathbf{E}_0(\mathbf{r}, \omega) + \frac{\omega^2}{\varepsilon_0 c^2} \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{G}}_0(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0; \omega) \hat{\alpha}_{\text{eff}} \mathbf{E}_0(\mathbf{r}_0, \omega), \quad (1)$$

where \mathbf{E}_0 is the incident field, ω is its angular frequency, $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{G}}_0(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0; \omega)$ is Green's function in free space and $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{eff}}$ is an effective polarizability of the tip, that depends on the properties of both the antenna and the sample. To find the antenna's effective polarizability, rewrite the local field at the antenna's location:

$$\mathbf{E}_1(\mathbf{r}_0, \omega) = \mathbf{E}_0(\mathbf{r}_0, \omega) + \frac{\omega^2}{\varepsilon_0 c^2} \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{G}}_0(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}; \omega) \hat{\alpha}_2 \mathbf{E}_2(\mathbf{r}, \omega). \quad (2)$$

Using the definition of the effective polarizability $\mathbf{p}_i = \hat{\alpha}_i \mathbf{E}_i = \hat{\alpha}_i^{\text{eff}} \mathbf{E}_0$, express $\hat{\alpha}_{\text{eff}}$ from the equations (1) and (2). It takes the form:

$$\hat{\alpha}_{\text{eff}} = \left(\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{I}} - \frac{\omega^4}{\varepsilon_0^2 c^4} \hat{\alpha}_1 \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{G}}_0(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}; \omega) \hat{\alpha}_2 \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{G}}_0(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{r}_0; \omega) \right)^{-1} \hat{\alpha}_1 \left(\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{I}} + \frac{\omega^2}{\varepsilon_0 c^2} \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{G}}_0(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}; \omega) \hat{\alpha}_2 \right). \quad (3)$$

Within the point-dipole approximation, the nanoantenna's dipole is placed at the center of curvature of the spheroidal tip [14], its longitudinal polarizability is equal to the polarizability of an elongated ellipsoid [15], and the transverse polarizability is determined by the Clausius-Mossotti formula [15]. If the tip polarizability is known $\hat{\alpha}_1$, the local field at the site of the molecule can be found using (1). Apart from the intrinsic polarizability, the Raman polarizabilities of the normal vibration modes of the molecule are also modified due to the local field.

The Raman polarizability is determined by the expression $\hat{\alpha}_n^R = (\partial \hat{\alpha}_2 / \partial q_n) q_n$, where q_n is normal coordinate of the molecular vibration mode. Raman-active mode radiates an optical field around the molecule at Raman-shifted frequency $\omega_n = \omega \pm \Omega_n$, which induces a Raman-shifted dipole on the tip. Due to the near-field optical interaction, both the probe and the molecule acquire additional dipole moments at the shifted frequency as well. As a result, the “antenna's tip + molecule” system when observed in the far-field behaves like a single dipole at Raman-shifted frequency ω_n with a total dipole moment equal to:

$$\mathbf{p}_{\text{out}}(\omega_n) \approx \left(\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{I}} + \frac{\omega_n^2}{\varepsilon_0 c^2} \hat{\alpha}_{\text{eff}}(\omega_n) \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\mathbf{G}}_0(\mathbf{r}_0, \mathbf{r}; \omega_n) \right) \hat{\alpha}_n^R \mathbf{E}_2. \quad (4)$$

In order to study the effects of polarization-controlled tip-enhanced Raman scattering, we carried out quantum chemistry simulation of the azo-chromophore

Figure 2. The calculated spectra of IR absorption (a) and non-resonant Raman scattering (b) for the cis-isomer and spectra of IR absorption (c) and non-resonant Raman scattering (d) for trans-isomer of the DO3 molecule. Scale factor $x = 0.981$

DO3 covalently attached to the CFAO polymer as a side chain (see. [12], Fig. 1). The calculation was performed for both isomers as observed in real azo-polymer under normal conditions. The optical parameters of the vibration modes of the DO3 molecule isomers were calculated *ab initio* at DFT level of theory, using Becke's hybrid exchange functional with the Lee-Yang-Parr correlation (B3LYP) [16,17], the triple-zeta basis set def2-TZVP [18], and Grimm's dispersion correction D3 with Becke-Johnson damping [19,20]. Since the film is considered to be thin (thickness < 5 nm), the influence of the rest of the surrounding polymer was not taken into account. The calculations were done with the Orca software [21] on the HPC cluster of Kazan Federal University.

The Fig. 2 demonstrates the calculated IR absorption and the tip-off non-resonant Raman spectra of unpolarized light for both the cis-isomer (blue graphs) and trans-isomer (red graphs) of the azochromophore, respectively. The calculated intensities of the vibration modes are shown by vertical stripes, the continuous spectrum is obtained via artificial Lorentzian broadening of the modes by 10 cm^{-1} . Normal mode frequencies was multiplied by a scaling factor of 0.981. Table 1 indicates the calculated (ν_c), scaled (ν_{sc}) and experimental (ν_{exp}) wavenumbers and the assignment of the vibration modes of both isomers of the molecule.

Comparing the infrared absorption spectra in Fig. 2a,c with each other, we note that the cis isomer in the CFAO polymer absorbs on average approximately 2 times less light than the trans isomer. Similarly, as seen from the Raman spectra in Fig. 2b,d, the cis isomer is on average about 5 times less Raman active than the trans isomer. Since the fraction of the cis isomer in the mixture is small compared to the fraction of the trans isomer at normal temperature [22], the low Raman activity and optical density of the cis isomer make it difficult to detect it in an CFAO film using conventional IR absorption and Raman spectroscopy.

In our simulation, the Z-axis was directed along the vector of the intrinsic dipole

Table 1. Vibration modes assignment of the spectra of the DO3 molecule

Cis isomer modes		Trans isomer modes		Spectral bands		Interpretation
ν_c/cm^{-1}	ν_{sc}/cm^{-1}	ν_c/cm^{-1}	ν_{sc}/cm^{-1}	$\nu_{\text{exp}}^{(\text{IR})}/\text{cm}^{-1}$	$\nu_{\text{exp}}^{(\text{Raman})}/\text{cm}^{-1}$	
1123	1102	1122	1101	1105	1104	C—NO ₂ stretching vibrations, C—H scissoring vibrations
1155	1133	1166	1144	1138	1139	C—NN stretching vibrations
1226	1203	1226	1203		1197	C—H scissoring vibrations
1281	1257	1279	1255	1242		C—NN, C—H stretching vibrations
1322	1297	1325	1300	1315	1315	C—NH, C—H stretching vibrations
1361	1335	1361	1335	1338	1336	NO ₂ symmetric vibrations
1438	1411	1438	1411	1387	1392	N=N, C—C ring stretching vibrations
1464	1436	1464	1436	1420	1423	C—H, N=N stretching vibrations
1506	1477	1492	1464	1457	1446	C—C rings anti-symmetric vibrations
1520	1491	1520	1491		1450	C—C ring, N=N stretching vibrations
1561	1531	1561	1531	1511		NO ₂ anti-symmetric vibrations
1635	1604	1635	1604		1587	C—C ring, polymer unit vibrations
1652	1621	1652	1621	1600		C—C ring, polymer unit vibrations

moment of the molecule; the spheroidal probe was located above it at a distance of 2 nm along the Z -axis. When calculating the effective polarizability tensors and Raman tensors using equations (4), (3) and (1), the sum of the near-field and mean-field parts of the Green's function of free space from [23] was used, the dielectric function of gold was taken from [24]. We simulated TERS in the system irradiated with the Z -polarized incident light with a wavelength of 632 nm. The Fig. 3 represents the TERS spectra in both polarizations of scattered light (referred to as Z and transverse, respectively) on both isomers of the molecule. As seen, the enhancement is almost absent in the transverse polarization (amplification by a factor of ~ 2), while in the longitudinal polarization it is of order $\sim 10^5$. In spite of the fact that the cis isomer is less Raman-active, its TERS response in transverse polarization exceeds the response of the trans isomer (Fig. 3b,d), while the response in the Z -polarization is ~ 7 times less than of trans-DO3. Consequently, the proposed model makes it possible to explain the dependence of the enhancement factor of the nanoantenna on the sample properties. Due to the different anisotropy of their polarizability tensor, both isomers of the molecule induce different additional dipole moment on the tip, which depends on the orientation of the principal axes of the tensor relative to the vector of the dipole moment of the isomer. This leads to different enhancement of certain vibration modes depending on their symmetry. The characteristic bands of symmetric and antisymmetric stretching vibrations of the nitro-group in the TERS spectra can be used to probe the cis isomer in the film. The nitro group in cis-DO3 turned almost at right angle compared to that of trans-DO3. When the tip brought to the molecule only vibrations aligned with the tip axis are effectively enhanced. Due to the different orientation of the nitro group relative to the dipole moment of the cis isomer, antisymmetric vibrations (1530 cm^{-1}) have a more intense band in the Z -polarized TERS spectrum, while symmetric stretching (1340 cm^{-1}) is more pronounced in the TERS spectrum in transverse polarization.

Figure 3. The simulated tip-enhanced Raman spectra of the DO3 molecule attached to the polymer repeat unit: a) cis-isomer in z-polarization of the scattered light, b) cis-isomer in transversal polarization, c) trans-isomer in z-polarization, d) trans-isomer in transversal polarization. Scale factor $x = 0.981$

3. Conclusion

Based on the proposed model, we have simulated tip-enhanced Raman spectra in longitudinal and transverse polarizations for the trans- and cis-isomers of the azochromophore DO3 covalently bound to the CFAO monomer. An explanation has been found for the dependence of the band enhancement in TERS spectra on both the polarization and optical properties of the sample. To determine the intrinsic optical parameters of the molecule, we have performed the numerical DFT-simulation and vibration modes assignment. Finally, we have theoretically demonstrated the possibility of probing the cis-isomer of the DO3 molecule in a polymer thin film using the TERS in longitudinal polarization. The analysis of the TERS spectra opens the way to determine the orientation not only of the anisotropic molecule as a whole, but also the orientation of its individual moieties in respect to its axis.

Acknowledgments. We are grateful to K.L. Shukhina and Prof. A.I. Fishman (Kazan Federal University) for their help in the analysis of vibration modes of the molecule and for providing us with the experimental IR and Raman spectra of the studied molecule.

The study was supported by the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation (state assignment no. 3.7737.2017/7.8) and performed by using the equipment of the Center of Shared Facilities of Kazan Federal University. The work was funded by the Ministry of Education and Science of the Russian Federation (contract no. 14.575.21.0149 (RFMEFI57517X0149)).

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Manuscript received 12/09/2017

ISSN 2541-7746 (Print)

ISSN 2500-2198 (Online)

UCHENYE ZAPISKI KAZANSKOGO UNIVERSITETA.
SERIYA FIZIKO-MATEMATICHESKIE NAUKI
(Proceedings of Kazan University. Physics and Mathematics Series)
2018, vol. 160, no. 1, pp. 61–71

Self-Consistent Model for Enhancement of the Raman Scattering of Polarized Light in Azo-Polymer Film with a Plasmonic Nanoantenna

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Received September 12, 2017

Abstract

This paper is devoted to modeling of the Raman scattering in the “antenna – sample” system. The system consists of an anisotropic azo-dye molecule attached covalently to a polymer chain and a plasmonic antenna located near the molecule. A model of near-field interaction in a system of dipoles has been proposed. The model takes into account changes in the polarizabilities of both the antenna and the molecule due to the mutual influence of their near field on each other. Based on the proposed model, the spectra of the tip-enhanced Raman scattering in longitudinally and transversely polarized field for both isomers of azo-chromophore have been simulated. The static polarizability of the molecule and the Raman-tensors of the vibration modes have been determined by the quantum chemical calculations of a molecule with one monomer according to the density functional theory.

Keywords: azo-chromophore, azo-polymer film, plasmonic antenna, tip-enhanced Raman scattering, near-field polarization, density functional theory, polarizability tensor, Raman tensor

Acknowledgments. We are grateful to K.L. Shukhina and Prof. A.I. Fishman (Kazan Federal University) for their help in the analysis of oscillation modes of the molecule and for obtaining and providing us with the experimental spectra of IR absorption and Raman scattering for the studied molecule.

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Figure Captions

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